

Peri-Implant Mucosa Anatomy

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Abstract

An implant is any material or object such as an alloplastic substance or tissue that is entirely or partially inserted or grafted into the body for the therapeutic, experimental, diagnostic, or prosthetic purpose. A dental implant is, therefore, a tapered or cylindrical post usually made of biometal titanium that works in place of the tooth root providing a sturdy foundation for tooth replacement. The vitality and health of the osseointegrated implant heavily rely on the supporting tissues that surround it, which give the implant with anchorage to the bone and provide a protective seal (Ivanovski and Lee, 2018). Earlier studies demonstrate a relationship between the opportunistic infective nature of peri-implantitis and periodontitis. Recommendations for future studies is that nonsurgical modalities have to be researched for treating peri-implantitis like the use of antibiotics and decontamination. This paper aims to shed light and enhance understanding of the anatomy of peri-implant mucosa by looking at it from different perspectives.

Peri-Implant Mucosa Anatomy

The soft tissues surrounding dental implants are known as peri-implant mucosa. The interface between mucosa and the implant is known as made up of an epithelium and a connective tissue. The epithelial barrier resembles junctional epithelium around teeth. Several similarities have been found between gingiva and peri-implant mucosa. In human biopsies, Collagen type 1 is the main component of the peri-implant mucosa supracrestal connective tissue. Both peri-implant mucosa and gingiva have similar fibronectin and collagen type 1, 3, 4 and 7 distribution.

The functional usefulness of oral implants depends on gingival or oral mucosa piercing in the oral cavity upon establishing a transmucosal connection between the inner dental implant and the external environment. Osseointegration is the direct connection amongst the bone and the alloplastic metallic implant. Titanium is biocompatible in physiological conditions and is the most commonly used biometal for implants. The tissues of peri-implant mucosa around the implant are similar to the gingiva situated around the teeth (Thoma et al., 2016).

Peri-implant mucosa is made up of a well keratinized oral epithelium, sulcular epithelium, junctional epithelium and the connective tissue below it. The basal lamina and hemidesmosomes are located between the epithelial cells and implant surface. The soft tissue interface. The biological width was a term coined by Garguilo who studied and described the dentogingival junction dimensions in human cadavers. It has an average size of 2.04mm (1.07 by 0.97mm) made up of junctional epithelium attachment and supra-alveolar connective tissues (Kan, Rungcharassaeng, Umezumi, and Kois, 2003). The bone encircling the tooth should not be encroached, with nearest actin remaining within 2mm. This kind of relationship of bone and its overlying tissues can also be seen around implants. Any changes in the relationship can be one of the reasons for the loss in the crestal bone at the early stages (Renvert and Polyzois, 2018).

The proliferation capacity of the junctional epithelium can cause a rapid epithelial cell migration when the fibrin clots and granulation tissues start forming at the implantation installation. When the cells get to the surface of the implant, they attach rapidly through the hemidesmosomes and the basal lamina. The contact between the epithelium and the implant is also one of the hypothesized ways by which possible attachments occur. The gingival tissues and the peri-implant sulcus share the same structural, functional, and ultrastructural characteristics. Studies on humans show that the epithelium that surrounds dental implants has similar differentiation and functional patterns as the gingival tissues. The granulation tissue that is attached to transmucosal components forms the principal factor stopping the apical migration of the epithelium. Berglundh (2011) posits that the interaction between the soft tissue and the titanium is the reason that prevents the epithelium from apical migration.

Adhesion of connective tissues during wound healing involves several factors and processes as the fibrin clot formation and adherence to the surface of the implant. Another factor is the fibrin clot adsorption to the surface of the implant. The extracellular matrix (ECM) proteins and connective tissue cells adsorption to the surface of the implant is also another process involved in the wound healing process (Jung, Heitz-Mayfield, Schwarz, and Groups of the 2nd Osteology Foundation Consensus Meeting, 2018). Another method or occurrence included during the process is the migration of the epithelial cells above granulation tissue or the fibrin clot. The zone close to the implant surface is composed of connective tissue and two parts. The first part is the 50 - μm inner area that is made up of fibers that resemble scar tissue, several fibroblasts scattered in close contact with the surface of titanium, and serve to maintain the seal between the oral environment and the peri-implant bone. The second part is the connective tissue that is comprised of fibers that run in different directions, together with blood vessels and

cellular elements. A 20-nm-wide proteoglycan layer separates the collagen fiber bundles and the connective tissues from the surface of the TiO₂ (Omori et al., 2018).

Naturally, teeth have nonkeratinized junction epithelium that attaches to the surface of the enamel through the desmosomes and the internal basal lamina. The nonkeratinized junction epithelium is among the junctional epithelial length. The peri-implant attachment to the surface of the implant, however, is limited to the apical area. The implant surface is parallel to the fibers, as observed only in human cadavers. Some researchers have found fibers in different locations (Heitz-Mayfield and Salvi, 2018). Fibers have also been observed in perpendicular directions that harbor the porous surfaces. This arrangement of fibers tends to depend on the mucosa quality, which is parallel to alveolar mucosa and perpendicular to keratinized mucosa. They are inserted perpendicularly into the tooth cementum. The arrangement of connective tissue encircling the tooth is one of the characteristics. The cementum and the bone harbor the dentogingival collagen fibers firmly as they are inserted into them perpendicularly and in an oblique direction. The dentogingival collagen fibers form a barrier protecting the epithelium from the always impending invasion by bacteria. There is weak mechanical resistance to the adhesion by connective tissue as compared to the natural teeth (Carmichael, McCulloch, and Zarb, 2017).

There is a sturdy connection between the periodontal ligament, the bone, and the tooth cementum. The ankylosis/osseointegration connection is rigid because periodontal ligament is absent around the implant. Lack of toughness may result in load transfer to the interface between the bone and the implant. In this case, there would be no compensatory movement of the tooth that can accommodate the occlusal disharmony. This situation can also lead to implant use in growing individuals. The periodontal ligaments, together with receptors that are highly sensitive, result in proprioceptive and tactile sensitivity around the tooth. When the periodontal ligaments

are absent, the physical sensation and reflex action felt around the tooth reduces. Periodontal ligaments can adapt, allowing the movements of the tooth except for the movements made by implants (Aslan, Tolay, and Gehrke, 2019).

There is a variation between the microbiota in partially edentulous patients and edentulous ones and those that have periodontal history. Teeth extraction eliminates *Porphyromonas gingivalis* and *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans* from the oral microbiota. Partially edentulous subjects experienced the development of microbiota around implants the same as those that occur in natural teeth. The rest of the teeth are the primary sources of putative pathogens, which reveal that the microbial status determines the fate that awaits new implants. Susceptibility to periodontitis may, therefore, lead to the development of peri-implantitis. Studies have shown that recently treated periodontitis is a risk factor for implant outcomes (Arvidson, Fartash, Hilliges, and Köndell, 2016).

The response to the healing of the tissues around the natural tooth and that around an implant varies. Teeth have better vascular supply as compared to implants. Tissue repair after an implant requires massive development of vasculature at the injury site for nutrient and oxygen delivery and cell debris removal to pave the way for healing. Inadequate vascular supply is caused by placing implants after flap elevation and affects the area between the marginal bone and the junctional epithelium. Inadequate vascular supply, in turn, may result in the extensive progression of plaque-associated inflammation.

Mucoperiosteal flap elevation leads to the resorption of postoperative bones. Tissue injury influences healing quality and speed. Small cleaned closed wounds are observed to heal faster than a little formation of a scar. On the other hand, large wounds are known to have a slow healing process with a significant amount of scarring. Some of the added benefits to flapless

surgery are the better supply of vasculature. It also retains the vitality of the supracrestal connective tissue surrounding the implant as compared to soft tissue with raised flaps. The surgery can result in cutting and damaging of the suprapariosteal vessels that form the sole supply of blood around implants. The mucosa surrounding the implant has a more closed smaller, clearer and smaller wounds in a flapless procedure than the flapless procedure. The flapless method helps preserve the vascularization of connective tissues, mainly when no single flap is reflected. The connective tissues of the crest, lateral to the surface of the implant, is supplied by the suprapariosteal vessels. The suprapariosteal vessel branches can be damaged or cut if soft tissue flaps are reflected.

Peri-implant and periodontitis have the same etiologies, meaning that the therapeutic approaches applied in both are also similar. Periodontal treatment and long term results are better in comparison with implants. The current lessons can host pathogens that will colonize the surface of the implant. It is, therefore, essential to treat and control periodontitis before an implanting procedure is performed. periodontitis can be treated by debridement of contaminated surfaces on the root and peri-implantitis treatment that dwells on implant surface decontamination. Decontaminating the surface of titanium can only be done through debridement even though its surface is rough and configured.

In adults, tooth loss can be caused by periodontitis, a fact that may have led to the conclusion that many patients that opt for implant reception have periodontal disease history. It takes several years to develop periodontitis and peri-implantitis infections (Araujo and Lindhe, 2018). Peri-implant mucosal tissues express more inflammatory response than the dentogingival unit due to the structural differences of tissues. Periodontal probing can be utilized to estimate the pocket depth, attachment level, width, and magical location. The biggest challenge in the

treatment of inflammations associated with teeth and implants is decontaminating the surface of the implant in the submucosal and surgical access. Many studies find a relationship between the opportunistic infective nature of peri-implantitis and periodontitis and the similarities and differences between the two. Therefore, future studies should look into nonsurgical modalities in the treatment of peri-implantitis, such as the use of antibiotics and decontamination. The association between the risk indicators should also be explored for development for literature into the subject matter.

The health of peri-implant depends on the health of the crestal bone levels and of soft tissues and biological factors responsible for their health. These factors include the factors around the health of gingival margin, peri-implant papilla and the peri-implant zone that acts as protective seal between the challenges posed by the external environment and the internal environment maintaining homeostasis.

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